

Cow Vigilantism as a Challenge Before Cow Protection Laws In India: A Critical Analysis

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Received: 04/03/2024

1st BPR: 10/03/2024

2nd BPR : 15/03/2024

Accepted : 21/03/2024

Abstract

Responding to constitutional mandate and deep public expectations in India, laws have been enacted by states to protect cows and promote its indigenous breeds. To satisfactorily achieve this objective, the stringency of these laws has been continuously increased by many states. However, there has been a recent rise in homicides or harassment related to cow protection in which some self-motivated groups of people, who consider themselves committed to cow protection, have become intolerant i.e. aggressive towards the minority Muslim and sometimes Dalit community. Such incidents are being perceived as a major challenge to the legal measures for cow protection. A section of critics believes that the increasing stringency of these laws is the main reason behind this extremism. So, the main question is whether cow-vigilantism is a problem arising from the strictness of cow protection laws or are there other reasons for it, such as increasing sensitivity of Hindu society towards cow protection or increasing intolerance towards cow slaughter? Are reasons like the excessive greed of cow as well as beef smugglers and the grave religious fanaticism of the Muslim community worth ignoring? The present study attempts to analyze these interrelationships logically.

Key words: Constitution of India, Cow Protection Laws, Cow Slaughter ban, cow vigilantism, Muslims killings, Hindu Fundamentalism, Fundamental Rights, Freedom of Religion.

Introduction

Constitution of India provides in Part IV some fundamental governing formulae for the country and the State is bound to be adhere with these directions, especially in creating regulations for the activities.¹ Article 48 in this Part abides the State particularly to endeavour prohibiting the slaughter of cows and its progeny.² Though Laws preventing the slaughter of cows are not new in India and in some states of British India are in existence since 1932³, but in response to the constitutional mandate and deep public expectations, more laws have been enacted by states to protect the cow's progeny and promote its indigenous breeds. Many of these including Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, and Karnataka, have made additional amendments and include stricter punishments for cow slaughter and some new activities like transportation, possession, sale of cattle and beef have also been criminalized in recent time. Currently, cow vigilantism (violence related to cow protection) is rising in some parts of the country. There has been a rise in homicides or harassment related to cow protection. In these activities some self-motivated groups of people, considering themselves committed to cow protection, have become intolerant i.e. offensively aggressive. Minority Muslims and sometimes members of Dalit community are being targeted in prompt reactions to cow slaughter related activities. Many times violence occurs on mere suspicions. This adoption of stricter measures in cow protection laws has coincident with an upsurge in cow-violence across the country. It is seen that the intensity of these incidences is so high in the states where the degree of punishment for cow slaughter is higher than other states.

Cow vigilantism incidents are being perceived as a major challenge to the legal measures for cow protection. A section of critics considers the increasing stringency of these laws as the main reason

behind this extremism. The analysis of the problem will help to understand its various characteristics. Though cow vigilantism is posing a serious challenge in society, strict provisions in cow protection laws is not the sole reason. The phenomenon is rising due to various independent reasons and there is no substantive relationship between cow vigilantism and the cow protection laws and their increasing stringency in recent past.

Incidents of Cow Vigilantism

To serve the cause assigned under Article 48 of the Constitution, almost all States in India have enacted laws to protect cows and her progeny. Though the legislations are declared valid and constitutional by the Supreme Court, implementation of these are facing many challenges on a number of grounds. Cow vigilantism is one of the serious concerns. The issue mostly criticised in the contemporary past is posing some grave challenges before the law enforcement agencies. The summary of discussion relating to this concern may go through the points mentioned here.

1. Cow Vigilantism Explained and Analysis of the Issue

Cow protection regulations are meant to be implemented by the State machinery. However, the machinery is reluctant and not acting at the required pace. So some groups of people are rising, having in their minds that taking action to enforce legal provisions is their *swadharma* (personal duty). Sometimes this 'endeavour' is reaching to violent parade. There are some incidents of killing the persons involved in 'law breaking'. Term, "Cow vigilantism" describes the current upsurge of violence happening in the name cow protection in India.

1.1 'Cow Protection' Spurs Vigilante Violence in India

In India, Hindus believe the cow to be a holy animal, so it's killing is forbidden in most parts as it hurts the majority sentiments. Since May 2015, the cow protectors have become more violent. Muslims and Dalits are especially being targeted in the acts of violence. A 12-year-old teenager has also become its victim. In July 2016, in Gujarat, vigilantes stripped four Dalits, tied them to a car, and thrashed with sticks and belts over doubt of cow slaughtering. There are many such brutal stories being floated in media quarters⁴. The incidences are not confined to cow slaughter. Nowadays violence and murder incidents of cattle vigilantism are being observed at an all-time high. Often vigilantes also attack vehicles transporting animals like buffalo. There are also complaints of attackers robbing transporters of their cash and essential items such as cellphones. Observers are noting "self-appointed 'cow protectors' driven by irresponsible populism are killing people and terrorizing minority communities."⁵ The recurring lynching incidents and targeted mob-violence against vulnerable groups in India now presenting serious challenges to crucial political activities like very existence of rule of law and fruitful electoral processes.⁶ Whatever is real picture, it may be another point of search, a section of analysts are claiming rising of BJP as reason behind this budding tendency⁷.

1.1.1 Vigilant and vigilantism defined

The word "vigilant" means to keep an eye out for possible difficulties or dangers. However, the term "vigilante" means a self-appointed person or a group of persons without authority, who gets involved in law enforcement on their own. This also includes those who take the law into their own hands to seek retribution when a crime is likely to have occurred.

1.1.2 Vigilantes and Vigilante Acts

Who are the Vigilantes:

The vigilantes in most of these incidents have come crosswise as organized bunches allegedly operating as criminal gangs. In many incidents of assaults and vandalism, prima-facie involvement of right wing groups like VHP, Bajrang Dal, Hindu Yuva Vahini (UP), Yuva Sena (Odisha), Gau Samvardhana Samiti (Maharashtra) among others was reported in the media. The main characteristics have been sought and expressed by a think tank thus, "The vigilantes are predominantly Hindu elites."⁸

1.1.3 Vigilante Crimes

On the basis of evident media reports some points related to acts of self-assessed protection groups may be categorised as follow:

Killings: Twenty incidents in which 29 people were killed. Encounter deaths arising out of an exchange of fire are part and parcel of vigilante justice which go unaccounted e.g. August 19, 2016 in Mahendragarh, Haryana.

Assault, Arson, Vandalism and Theft: At least sixty episodes of physical assault and three of sexual assault. Arson, vandalism of vehicles, shops, homes, theft of valuables are recurring aspects of vigilantism. Arson often accompanies protests and rioting by gaurakshaks.

Stripping and tonsuring: There were four incidents of stripping across 2016 and 2017, and one of tonsuring in January 2018. The allegations against victims were theft and cow slaughter. Some of these 'punishments' such as tonsuring of two Dalits for alleged theft and stripping are extremely cruel, feudal as well as casteist forms of penalty.

Humiliation and coercion: These include coercive incidents where Muslim victims have been forced to eat cow dung and drink urine, to say Jai Shri Ram, and squirted with urine to 'purify' alongwith punishments by caste panchayats as atonement for accidentally slaying calves.

Extortion: Extortion and theft are the most overt features of this criminal economy, with an abrupt and a domino effect. The increasing such extortion between Goa and Karnataka have been reported in several other parts of India where gaurakshaks, who carry identity cards, stop trucks and board on asking payment to let the trucks pass.

Seizures of cattle and vehicles: Seizure of cattle by gaurakshaks and police is reported in a number of cases. In some instances, reports mention that the cattle were sent to gaushalas, in others the cattle have either been directly appropriated by the vigilante or been handed over to them by the police. Several of these are incidents of "tip-offs."

1.1.4 Profiling the victims

In the most incidents of vigilantism, Muslims were targeted (about 75%) and in some cases Dalits (about 12%) were also targeted. These figures are based on 106 incidents where it was possible to trace the community of the victims. The victims of the attacks are farmers at some places and cattle and meat traders at others. The list also includes milk-suppliers, butchers, tanners, drivers, shepherds etc. The attack methods of cow vigilantes differ against Muslims and Dalits. Attacks against Muslims are targeting their food habits and businesses, particularly the meat trade, transportation of dairy animals and beef, which provide very basic livelihoods. A clear communal character is visible in cases of vigilance against Muslims. However, in many of the reported cases, incidents of violence against Dalits have been in the context of disposing of animal carcasses and skinning them. In fact, it is a caste-based and 'imposed' business. Although the charges brought against the victims by the vigilantes were of theft and cow slaughter, the true reason behind it was Dalits' refusal to clean the bodies of dead animals in protest. In many cases, Dalits wanted to move away from such work for the sake of education or to join some respectable professions.

1.2 Distinct Features of Recent Concerns

1.2.1 Government Silence and Denial

State machinery responded in an improper way. For instance, the State's government, in the highly discussed attack and Murder case of Pehlu Khan, did not even condemn the killing. However, the Home Minister of the State sought to shield vigilantes: "People know cow trafficking is illegal, but they do it. *Gau bhakts* [Cow worshippers] try to stop them. There's nothing wrong with that but it's a crime to take the law in their hands."⁹

Instead of filing a complaint against the attackers, the police first filed a complaint against Khan and others under the Rajasthan Bovine Animal (Prohibition of Slaughter and Regulation of Temporary Migration or Export) Act, 1995 for illegally exporting cattle and showing cruelty to them. (The alleged offenses under the Act carry a maximum prison sentence of five years). In response, ex-officials of the Rajasthan government reacted harshly saying that failure to take prompt action would be a "mockery of good governance, causing minorities to lose faith in the government's ability to protect their rights."¹⁰

1.2.2 States Prompting Cow Protection

Amidst violence concerned with cow protection is on rise, even the government office bearers in many States look determined and ready to work more for cattle protection cause. Critics in or off the media spheres are coming heavily on them for such an attitude.

“In March 2017, the Gujarat government made slaughtering a cow punishable by life in prison. In Chhattisgarh, the ... chief minister said, “We will hang those who kill cows.” In 2016, the Haryana government decided to give licenses to some cow protection groups to help the police keep a check on alleged cow smuggling.”¹¹

Vigilantes often travel on highways as patrol parties. They also stop and check vehicles for cattle, intimidate drivers and react violently if cows are found in vehicles. These vigilantes have physically attacked legitimate cattle transporters, even those carrying buffaloes. Many times, the action taken by the law enforcement machinery is not proper and always inadequate.¹²

1.2.3 State collusion in vigilantism

Vigilantism blooms through the active collaboration of the police and the promotion of vigilantes, while simultaneously further victimizing victims by entangling them in criminal cases. Civil society documents testify that the police and senior administrative officials are openly allowing the criminal activities of vigilante groups. The actions taken against victims prove to be much more serious in severity than those taken against vigilantes.

“The police often stand by, careful not to interfere with the actions of the majority community. Both mobs and police have regularly treated victims of cow vigilantism...in ways that de-victimise these individuals. Rather than taking swift action against perpetrators, law enforcement agencies act mostly against the victims themselves.”¹³

1.2.4 Describing Vigilantism with God Connection

Not only in ancient India but also at times in modern times, members of lower castes have been killed at the altar of angry and demonic 'gods'. Dwarven minds constantly attack our bodies and souls to 'entertain' powerful gods who have never been seen and have no clear evidence of their existence. In modern and democratic India, when and why did we decide that we would continue to believe that the behavior of alleged desecrators is worthy of brutality and murder in defense of sacred demands?

1.3 Severity of Law and Vigilantism

Let us now consider some cow protection laws passed by different states in India. In Jharkhand, transportation, trade or possession of beef and even abetment and attempt to commit these offenses carry a minimum rigorous imprisonment of one year and a maximum of ten years. Whereas, in Rajasthan the punishment of imprisonment is up to five years for violation of law and committing such offences. In Uttar Pradesh, there is a provision of rigorous punishment of up to seven years for transportation or sale of beef or animals of bovine origin. Even merely attempting to commit such crimes can lead to a jail term of up to three and a half years. In Uttarakhand, sale, transportation and even possession of beef is punishable with rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of three years and a maximum of seven years, and in Gujarat, such acts are punishable with imprisonment of up to three years. The sale of beef is banned in Haryana, for violation of which there is a provision of rigorous imprisonment for a minimum of three years and a maximum of five years. In Goa and Punjab, the punishment for possessing beef is two years, and in Delhi, Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh, the punishment for this offense is one year. Its harshness can be estimated from the fact that in many states the onus of proving innocence against the charge of crime is on the accused and the crimes have been categorised as 'non-bailable'. Where possession is prohibited, it is made an offense in itself, regardless of the amount in possession and whether or not it is offered for sale. The provisions regarding slaughter are becoming more stringent.

If different incidents occurring across the country are analyzed in the background of cow protection laws from various aspects, such as the location of the incident, the trigger of the attack and the subsequent state responses, significant links between vigilante violence and state-specific legislation are revealed. It seems that strictness of penal provisions is directly proportionate to lynching incidences in the State concerned. States with the strictest laws reported higher lynching incidents. It supports what Edmund Burke said, “Bad laws are the worst form of tyranny”. We are also witnessing the harsh reality that in states where there is no specific law in place prohibiting cow slaughter, no lynching or any other criminal incident of similar nature has been reported¹⁴. It tends to conclude that states with the strictest laws reported higher incidents of lynching. The principle or reason behind the situation and relationship between two factors has to be sought. It may provide some sort of solution.

1.4 Advent of New 'Crimes'

The States tend to widen the scope of the protection umbrella under societal and other pressures. The result of creating new crimes by increasing the scope of crimes is that it increases the number of potential criminals and this happens in the field of vigilance also. Criminalizing cow slaughter mainly involves slaughterhouses, traders and butchers directly involved in the slaughter of animals. But now criminalizing the transport, sale and possession of cattle or beef potentially affects any person directly or indirectly associated with cattle or beef, such as farmers, consumers, transporters, hoteliers, as well as those involved in handling the meat. Or someone working in the leather trade, etc., can be proven guilty of the crime. Newly declared crimes would lead to increased risks of both – prosecution and vigilantes attacks against them. Severe legal consequences are tending to grow off the way settlement possibilities too, if the cases of confrontations occur between cow traders and vigilantes. Really it will be a new cause of concern on the part of law and order situation.¹⁵ The question of criminalizing beef consumption is also adding new possibilities of making a new group of criminals in the society as eating cow beef is not simply a food habit or 'an act', but a politically embedded as inherent and integral part of Muslim identity. It is being done despite the fact that 'there is no constitutional mandate to prohibit beef consumption'. In fact the mandate encourages the State to "take steps for preserving and improving the breeds, and prohibiting the slaughter, of cows and calves and other milch and draught cattle"¹⁶.

1.5 Impacts of Cow Vigilantism

Vigilantism is causing tension in social life. It is also reported that the incidents are responsible for economic loss.

Due to the stigma associated with cow slaughter, many farmers have turned to buffalo rearing. Wherever cow vigilantes were most feared, the cow population declined due to the above reason, and the buffalo population witnessed a significant upturn.¹⁷

Though it is seen that inclination towards buffaloes is a distinct reason for the trend of decreasing cow population, vigilantism may also be attributed as a great cause. People in the tannery business are currently able to get only 4,000 hides per month, which has crossed the earlier level of at least 25,000. This is because even truck drivers transporting legally obtained buffalo hides fear attacks from vigilantes. Shedding of staff working in such businesses is also likely as shortage of the inventory.¹⁸ Another report also supports the difficulty caused and "fear of being attacked by Hindu vigilantes"¹⁹. Fear is causing more harm than any other thing. "Selling red meat, even goat meat, in a BJP-ruled state is now injurious to one's health. Who would want to risk the wrath of the vigilantes?"²⁰

Particularly in Uttar Pradesh – the largest producer of carabeef in India – from Ghaziabad to Ghazipur, the sale of buffalo meat has come to a complete stop across. Animals' (needed for slaughter) movement across the state has come to a complete halt due to high presence of cow vigilantes on major highways and even in interiors.²¹ While the incidence of cow vigilante groups is not novel in the state, they have become very active after the changed political scenario.

1.6 Vigilantism and the State Action

State is not in procrastination mode and is responding in both directions. If there is strict action against the perpetrators, illegal transportation and illegal slaughter houses then it is evident that vigilantes are also on radar. Police is instructed to register FIRs against law breaking vigilantes to prepare dossiers on them after identification.²² Reports quoted the statement of UP State head of police (DGP) Sulkhan Singh – "These people/organizations should be informed that they do not have a right to act illegally by taking the law into their hands."²³ Officials in other areas with such disturbances are also cautious to deal the tension with rough hands. The Supreme Court of India has also responded to the incidents strictly. "In April, 2018 the Court issued notices to the state governments of Rajasthan, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Jharkhand and Maharashtra to respond to enforcing strict bans on cow vigilantes."²⁴

1.6.1 Vigilantism Criticized

It is widely felt that 'right wing' organizations like *Sangh Parivar* and BJP are highly criticized for the rise of cow vigilantism in India. The real picture seems something different from the acclaimed portrait. Biren Singh has said that State governments should immediately stop violence in the name of

cow protection or checking beef consumption. They should not allow criminals to cause further destruction or spread misinformation widely. Mr. Singh is one of the chief ministers leasing the BJP led State governments. He headed ruling coalition (a political accumulation) in Manipur.²⁵

1.6.2 Vigilantes Sentenced

In June 2017, Aleemuddin alias Asghar Ali was allegedly killed by a mob of over 100 people. When he was returning home after buying meat from the local market, he was beaten to death by the mob. The incident occurred on the suspicion that he was carrying cow flesh. A fast-track court of additional district and session judge in Jharkhand sentenced 11 people guilty under section 302 (murder) of the Indian Penal Code (IPC), to life imprisonment for lynching the 55-year-old man. A fine of Rs 2,000 each was also imposed on the culprits. The court did not pronounce its verdict on the 12th minor convicted in the case. The court has also sent its order to the District Legal Services Authority to take necessary steps for compensation to the victim's family.²⁶

1.7 Smuggling Versus Vigilantism: Serious Perspective in Debate

The suspicions of Gaurakshaks are not always baseless. The cow-hide trade possesses high temptation amongst the traders. The allegation that cattle traders are under severe fear becomes false if we look at the situation created by these law perpetrators. A cow could bring back anywhere between Rs 80,000 and Rs 90,000. Cow smugglers are, therefore, completely unconcerned by the increasing number of fatal confrontations with vigilantes. Cow hide, used in making various leather goods, is a big temptation for the smugglers.²⁷

Indian meat is considered to be of very high quality due to its extremely low amount of saturated fat and is also free from harmful substances. Not only the meat but also the leather of Indian cattle, especially calf leather, is in high demand in the international markets. This illegal business in Mewat region (Rajasthan), as like many parts of India, has well planning and well thought destinations. Once the smuggled cows cross into Haryana from their source point, the rampant cattle mafia takes over. From there, the cows are transported to Assam and West Bengal through Uttar Pradesh for finally smuggled into Bangladesh. From there they are taken to abattoirs from where their hide is transported to tanneries. This is an organized sector filled with perpetrators and law enforcement agencies are highly reluctant in this region. The high profitability of the meat trade has created huge stakes. Lavish profits have increased the meat lobby's ability to spend lavishly in negotiations with officials. Although export of beef is not legally permitted, it is still exported clandestinely by being labelled as 'buffalo meat'. A very strong nexus has come into existence between the meat lobby, corrupt politicians and the bureaucracy. Facilitative policies are made to promote meat trade, all kinds of other incentives, protection and various subsidies are provided to the sector and the booties are shared by the three sectors of this nexus. This is a much claimed reason for the rise of cow protection groups across Indian society. If vandalism is treated as a serious concern, then one should think of the acts done by these smugglers. Smugglers are not alone in this work. For example, in various parts of Mewat, including Kaman, Pahari, and Deeg in Bharatpur district, and Govindgarh and Ramgarh in Alwar district, local people in a large number are involved in smuggling.²⁸

1.8 The other Face of 'Killings'

Not all minority killings are related to cow protection and vigilantism. There are many other reasons for these attacks. There have also been incidents of violence instigated by hatred during festivals like Ram Navami in different parts of the country. Sometimes with provocation regarding Azaan and Namaz (Gurugram in Haryana) and sometimes with open violence against people considered as Muslims (trains in UP and Haryana). One thing to be noted is that most of the victims in lynching cases are almost poor fellows. Interestingly rumors are attributed as the main cause of attacks added with rampant social media effect.

"Most of these attacks were based on rumours sparked by accusations that the victims, almost always Muslims, slaughtered or smuggled cows. The content of these rumours and fears often circulating on social media take the shape of communal stereotypes of victims

either eating beef or intending to do so, or showing any form of perceived disrespect for cows, which is broadly claimed as a motivation for lynching.”²⁹

1.8.1 'We don't Go After Innocents'

The persons involved in cow protection activities are self-acclaimed law binding individuals. They think it fit to call the Police if any incidence of cow slaughter and cow smuggling comes to their knowledge. Use of force becomes unnecessary as they move organized in large groups.³⁰

2. Reasons Responsible for Cow Vigilantism

Cow vigilantism is rising due to various socio-cultural factors varying their effects in distinct regional and political contexts. We can summarize some of them as follow:

2.1 Cultural Identity Concerns: Hindu cultural identity is deeply attached with cow protection and veneration. In Hinduism cows are considered as mother and grown cattle wealth symbolises abundance. Cow protection is realized as a religious obligation by groups and individuals. Indeed, “the protection of cows is perceived as a way to preserve cultural values, heritage, and a sense of belonging”³¹.

2.2 Threats to Rural Economics: Livestock economics is a very crucial aspect in rural areas. Considerations like maintenance of investments in dairies as well as the agriculture sector, and protecting their labourers’ interests can drive individuals to take extreme measures to guard cattle. Farmers in rural India are highly adept with cattle rearing and dairy farming as crucial sources of income. The illegal trade of cows may prove disastrous to poor farmers in this country. Cow smugglers offer ingenuine higher prices to get cattle for slaughter and disrupt local economies this way, particularly in rural areas. They are snatching their cattle wealth. The desire to protect their cattle from smugglers if not satisfied by permissible ways may become a serious cause of cow vigilantism in rural communities. Linkage to organized crime networks is also accelerating the seriousness. There is a nexus between cow smugglers and organized crime networks operating in illegal, inhuman and prohibited cross-order businesses. Resultantly, to combat the issue is a serious challenge for law enforcement agencies. This is exacerbating tensions and prompting vigilantism in response.

2.3 Legal Ambiguities or Gaps: There are legal ambiguities or gaps in cattle protection laws regarding the slaughter or transportation. It creates a suitable situation for self-proclaimed cow vigilantes. They will tend to enforce the law on their own to mitigate the perceived absence of legal enforcement.

2.4 Garnering Political Support: Cow protection is a politically sensitive issue. Supporting this cause can be exploited by certain people to mobilize electoral support. Populism attached with it advances political agendas promptly. Critics are connecting these incidents with the BJP’s rise after 2014 elections, too.³² Groups of hidden interest may use public sentiment to polarise and harness political support. Vigilantism may also rise this way.

2.5 Social Tension: Conflict related to religion or community, a harsh and growing trait in Indian society, generates unique tension. THE ROOT CAUSE has its depth in historical fact of prolonged Muslim rule over subcontinent.³³ These existing social tensions set the stage for cow vigilantism, ‘leading to confrontations and acts of violence.’³⁴

2.6 Lack of Trust in Law Enforcement Agencies: Enforcement agencies are becoming trustless and the judicial system is perceived as inefficient, corrupt and biased. It is proving enough to drive people or groups in public to take matters into their own hands as the only perceived way to ensure justice or protect their community’s interest. This distrust is aggravating the situation and vigilantes’ activities are gathering mass support.

2.7 Impacts of Cow Smuggling: Cow smuggling is emerging as one of the grave factors that contribute to spread cow vigilantism extensively. It is not to say that vigilantism is the result of ‘a complex web of socio-economic, religious, and legal issues’. This web is a creation of illegal activities woven around the generation of lucrative sum through illegal cross-border transportation of cows for slaughter.³⁵

2.8 Misinformation: In some cases, misinformation may be terrible. Rumours surrounding cow slaughter are contributing to the rise of vigilantism. Lack of awareness about the law enforcement agencies may instigate, in some cases, individuals to take the law into their own hands.

Increasing Stringency: An Analysis

Table: 1 - Chronology of Punishment in Legislations

S.N.	States	Inception	Jail Term (years)	Latest Amendment
1.	Telangana	(1950)	0.5	1950
2.	West Bengal	1950	0.5	1950
3.	Assam	1951	0.5	1962
4.	Bihar	1955	0.5	1962
5.	Andhra Pradesh	1977	0.5	1977
6.	Odisha	1960	2	1960
7.	Pondicherry	1960	2	1960
8.	Maharashtra	1976	5	1995
9.	Himachal	1979	5	2010
10.	Delhi	1994	5	1994
11.	Uttar Pradesh	1955	7	2002
12.	Madhya Pradesh	1959	7	2006
13.	Karnataka	1964	7	New law 2020
14.	Chhattisgarh	2004	7	2004
15.	Punjab	1955	10	2011
16.	Rajasthan	1995	10	1995
17.	Jharkhand	2005	10	
18.	Uttarakhand	2007	10	2015
19.	Haryana	2015	10	2015
20.	Gujarat	1954	Life	2017

One fact about the punishments provided by the State enactments is very clear on the basis of analysis provided in the aforementioned table. The earlier enactments in time show a milder approach than the later ones. Severity of penalty goes gradually harder and recent enactments pose a hard threat against perpetrators. In the beginning, laws made in the fifties were merely regulatory. It was even termed as 'slaughter manuals'. Enactments up to 1977 (Andhra Pradesh) represent this category. Very low intensity penalty as well as a mild approach to perpetrators is the basic character of these 'manuals'. Another distinct feature may be noted as reluctance of amending the statutes concerned. There found no adaptation according to changing time and circumstances though scenarios of the subject concerned have been changed drastically all over the country, including the States in consideration. The Seventies of the last century observed some changes in the approach to the problem and the concerned legislatures adopted some harder ways than earlier to deal with the prohibition of cow slaughter issue. Penalty was increased here and the period of imprisonment goes up to two years, harder in some ways in comparison to mere six months in earlier instances. Two representatives are available in the table of the trend – Odisha and Pondicherry. Nineties brought some seriousness to the point of penalty. The legislations enacted in or amendments brought therein in this phase enhanced their focus to attend to the problem with the right hand. Period of imprisonment and sum of fine went much further. Term of imprisonment for violation of rules was fixed up to 5 years accompanied with a higher fine. Delhi, Himachal Pradesh and Maharashtra make elements of this set. Latter two States adopted the trend through amendments in their statute book but the enactment of Delhi was made originally in this period as frontrunner. In next generation rules penalty finds more attention to curb the menace posed before society. Greed of the perpetrators was increasing and trade of cow flesh was emerging as a lucrative business. These severe situations were to be tackled with a hard hand and posing a serious threat before destroyers of cow wealth was the only way. The enactments and rules too, particularly

brought up in the twenty-first century, increased the penalty and the term of imprisonment was increased further up to seven years. The State of Uttar Pradesh is a particular example of this group. Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka and Chhattisgarh are other members in this category. The highest term of imprisonment, let the State of Gujarat be an exception, in the cow slaughter legislation is fixed at ten years. Punjab, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, Uttarakhand and Haryana have fixed this type of severe penalty in their respective laws. Though this trend was first initiated in 1995 by Rajasthan but gained real pace in the first decade of the current century. The state of Gujarat is the latest case where life term imprisonment may be fixed as punishment alongwith a severe fine which may be up to Rupees five lakhs. In 2017, the rule was brought into statute book through an amendment. It is noteworthy here that severe penalties are the need of hour and emerging as a great tool of cow protection. If implemented seriously these penal provisions are posing a proper threat to perpetrators. It is evident from the instance of Uttar Pradesh where the concerned rules are being followed with increased interest.

In recent years, cow protection laws have been gradually made stricter. However, incidents of cow vigilantism have also increased in these years. It has been observed in the previous section that there are several obvious reasons for the increase in cow-vigilantism. There is no clear connection between strengthening the laws and the increase in these incidents, indeed. So it is not right at all to perceive the rising stringency of cow protection laws as the sole reason. In fact, at present these incidents have been stopped or are showing a significant reduction, while the laws are still in place. The vigilance of the administration in implementing the penal laws has increased and the administration of peace and order has been strengthened. For this reason, the incidents of cow vigilantism are gradually decreasing.

Conclusions and Suggestions

The increasing incidents of cow vigilantism are becoming a major challenge to peace and order. The main goal of law is to establish peace in the society. There is a definite goal of making laws and laws are not made unnecessarily. Cow protection is a topic deeply linked to culture in India. It has many deep economic and social implications behind its influence in culture. Cow wealth has been a measure of prosperity in India and is also a major component of the rural economy in particular. In such a situation, the sentiments related to cow slaughter can be easily guessed. Cow protection laws are a result of the State's recognition for the inherent feelings amongst the masses. The prevalent practices causing danger to societal peace are eradicated by these laws and precious wealth is protected. Despite the presence of cow protection laws for early days of the Indian republic, due to weak measures provided in the legislations, cow slaughtering and cross border smuggling was drastically rising. Resultantly, the grave depletion of cattle wealth emerged as a new challenge before society. The rise of militancy among the people for cow protection is not linked to the rise of BJP. In fact, BJP is increasing its stature by supporting public sentiments.

Adopting stricter measures for cow protection was the result of depletion of cattle numbers as effective mechanisms may be introduced for protection of agricultural animals. Risk to these animals was causing serious concerns and abrupt vigilantism. As the agencies are paying proper attention, incidents related to cow vigilantism are decreasing in numbers as well as their seriousness. To mitigate these incidents, I feel no need to deplete the legal measures. In spite of it measures suggested hereunder may be more helpful to face the challenges posed by cow vigilantism in India.

- Drop in cow smuggling
- Reduction of the economic risks
- Robust law enforcement efforts
- Dismantling organized crime networks
- International cooperation

References:

- ¹ Article 37, The Constitution of India.
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